

RELIABLE DESIGN AND FABRICATION COMPOSITE HIGH PERFORMANCE MARINE STRUCTURES

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ABSTRACT

The Advanced Research Projects Agency (ARPA) has under taken a major technology effort to develop reliable designs which demonstrate lower cost using advanced fabrication methods for marine structures. The proof-of-concept prototype selected to demonstrate these technologies is a thick-section, Composite Dry Deck Shelter, and a near term non-man-rated Composite Storage Capsule, which provides a hydrostatic pressure resistant dry environment. This paper discusses these programs, as well as, results of the building block approach to achieve the program objectives which includes: design, fabrication, inspection and testing of various structural subelements and structural models. The successful test results on 1.22 m (48 inch) diameter, thermoset and thermoplastic, structural models to collapse under external pressure are also presented.

INTRODUCTION

Composite materials offer the potential for reduced structural weight, improved corrosion resistance and associated reduction in maintenance and enhanced stealth and survivability over existing metals for marine structures. Composites have two to five times the strength-to-weight ratio of high strength steels, thus substantially reducing weight. Composites are non-magnetic and can be made acoustically transparent. Stealth is enhanced by the intrinsic damping of polymer composites due to the resin, fiber, layup or architecture or through the use of constrained layers. The composite fabrication process also makes the materials architecture readily acceptable for embedded sensors as built-in quality assessment and health monitoring tools for the life of the ship.

However, the composites selected must also demonstrate their benefits at competitive costs with present systems. In order to be competitive, low-cost, innovative material forms and low cost manufacturing and design concepts must be developed for composites while achieving the high quality levels demanded for man-rated marine structures.

Recognizing the benefits of composites, ARPA has initiated a major technology effort in developing and demonstrating affordable composites fabrication processes for application to military and commercial marine applications. This effort involves a number of major aerospace, shipbuilding, composite materials suppliers, and government laboratories. The focus of the program is the use of advanced fabrication methods such as in-situ consolidation, non-autoclaving curing, and advanced fiber placement process for both thermoplastic and thermoset composites.

In-situ consolidation of thermoplastics or Cure-on-the Fly™ (COTF™) of thermosets in concert with automated fiber placement and real time in-process control may be the most effective solution to alleviate the high cost and quality deficiencies associated with hand layup, filament

winding, bagging and autoclave cycles. Precise automated placement of fibers with multi-axes winders over complex mandrels will permit continuous, rapid, reproducible fabrication of marine structures with relatively high throughputs and near zero porosity and precise resin control without the use of vacuum bagging and autoclaving. Furthermore, the costs involved with acquiring, operating and maintaining an autoclave are eliminated as well. For a full scale marine structure, these costs would be prohibitive.

Other promising architectures such as two and three dimensional woven fabrics and braided structures offer the potential to produce net shape preforms continuously, as well as provide a product form with improved damage tolerance and impact resistance with lower cost. Combined with resin transfer molding (RTM), these technologies also offer a cost reduction potential for composite submarine structures.

In addition, to fabrication and cost, other technical issues such as reliable design criteria, safety aspects (fire, smoke, and toxicity), joining/attachment methods, damage resistance, cyclic and durability performance, inspection and repair must be addressed before composites can be extensively used and accepted for full scale production.

PROGRAM OVERVIEW

The objective of this ARPA thick composites technology program is to develop the technology, experience, and confidence needed to exploit the potential benefits of composite materials for submarine pressure hulls, components and marine structures through the orderly transfer of the proven aerospace composite technology. The results will culminate in the development of a reliable, cost effective, proven construction capability for a full-scale, thick section, proof-of-concept, Composite Dry Deck Shelter (CDDS) which is seen as a required step before prototype submersible construction. The completion of the CDDS program will deliver preliminary design criteria, inspection and repair standards, material specifications and large thick composite structure manufacturing methods that have been validated through proof-of-concept design/manufacture. These documents will provide guidance, technical basis and recommendations for thick composite usage by other government agencies and U. S. industry.

The ARPA CDDS program has focused on the development of non-autoclave curing and in-situ consolidation for large, thick section composite submersible structures to achieve affordability [1]. Control of resin content, resin flow, pot life, consolidation, porosity levels and partial curing during fiber placement appears the most practical for submarine structures. One of the primary cost reductions for composite fabrication will be elimination of the large autoclaves necessary for curing. Since the material is being fully consolidated on-the-fly, on-line NDI is possible. A goal of the program is to produce autoclave quality parts with the void content below one percent. Another is to achieve high throughputs in the order of 91 kg/hr (200 lb/hr) while maintaining as-fabricated costs below \$220/kg (\$100/lb) for pressure hull structure.

To achieve the program objectives, an interactive three-phase approach, progressing from design/concept development to fabrication and testing of sub-scale test articles to fully develop the technology, has been implemented and will lead to a full-scale man-rated Composite Dry Deck Shelter in Phase III. Due to the lengthy process required for the certification of a man-rated structure and in order to rapidly prototype the benefits of the composite technology developed, a near term, non-man-rated Composites Storage Capsule will be fabricated using the CDDS lessons learned for the Office of Naval Research (ONR).

The investigations, trade-offs, concept development, design and manufacturing and testing have been apportioned among proven composite design and manufacturing technology industry leaders with GD/EBDiv serving as the composite pressure hull designer and design integrator to insure transition of technology to the U. S. marine industry. Figure 1 lists main program participants and their subcontractors. Figure 2 shows the areas of responsibility for the fabrication of the CDDS. This paper will discuss the status of that part of Phase I work being performed and the ONR Composite Storage Capsule, Figure 3.

Phase II entails the design, fabrication and test of a half-scale validation model of the CDDS to be used in Phase III.

DESIGN CONSIDERATIONS

Unlike metals where properties of the material remain constant through the fabrication process, the properties of composites depend on how they are processed. Therefore, the manufacturing

process must be considered early in the design stage. The composites engineer must be knowledgeable of the available fabrication processes as well as inspection procedures for quality assurance to obtain a cost effective design. The success of the finished composite part to sustain the operating loads for the life of the structure relies on an integrated design process between engineering, manufacturing and inspection.

The integrated design process involves a building block approach progressing from design, build, test and evaluation and using lessons learned, before proceeding to the next phase. Design guidelines were developed based on material lamina and laminate strain allowables obtained from coupon tests with knockdowns for statistical variations, manufacturing process, environmental effects, thickness, curvature, stress risers, etc. and realistic factor of safety. These allowables must reflect the fabrication process but without overburdening the benefits of composites with severe conservatism and updated as confidence and test data are developed.

MATERIAL SELECTION

In addition to the strength, stiffness, lightweight, fatigue resistance, chemical/corrosion resistance, damping, non-magnetic, reduced maintenance and tailorability requirements, the material system must provide damage resistance, moisture resistance and address fire, smoke, and toxicity (FST) requirements [2]. The FST criteria for use of composites aboard Navy vessels requires: 1) low non-toxic smoke generation, 2) sufficient fire resistance not to be a source of spontaneous combustion, 3) secondary ignition of the composite will not result in rapid spreading of fire. Thermoplastic crystalline material systems AS4/PEEK and AS4/PPS were selected to provide the damage resistance, strength, stiffness, moisture resistance, and FST improvements [3] as well as providing affordability and compatibility with the fabrication process. An extensive material database was also available for AS4/PEEK thermoplastic for aerospace applications. This data assisted in determining material allowables without excessive coupon testing costs.

ANALYSES

To address the structural design problem properly and to design for producibility, it is important to establish the relationship of the manufacturing process to theoretical design. With care in the material selection and lay-up, composites can meet any of the design criteria. The validation and correlation of the design and fabrication methods to theoretical design relies on the testing of structural elements and structural models.

Detail finite element analyses were performed using C. T. Sun's theory [4] to establish 3D material properties for the various lay-ups. These smeared 3D properties are used to perform stress analyses with 2D axi-symmetric and 3D solid elements with the ABAQUS finite element code [5]. A ply by ply analysis would be performed on the "hot spots" where there are high stress/strain gradients, stress risers or singularities. In the building block approach, failure is predicted using the physically based modified Hashin's failure criterion [6].

JOINING OF COMPOSITES

Joining of composites is another critical design consideration. Because of the required size of the marine structure, joints between major sections will be necessary and desirable in full scale production. Joints are required for assembling major structural subsections fabricated by different methods such as compartment bulkheads, hatches for loading decks, major machinery and structure during construction and for replacing/refurbishing major items during overhaul. Joints are also desirable to accommodate structural modules such as the modules comprising the Composite Dry Deck Shelter. The design of the joint is critical in maintaining the weight and performance benefits of composites. Improperly designed joints can negate any weight reduction. By their nature, joints represent reductions in strength and produce stress-concentration sites where fatigue damage can initiate, and they are more demanding in composites because they lack the ductility to redistribute loads like metals. The CDDS modules incorporate composite/titanium joints to allow for the sections to be assembled and disassembled. A detailed trade-off of joint concepts versus discriminators such as weight, cost, inspectability, assembly, repair and performance was performed in selecting the CDDS joint concepts. Successful tests to collapse were also performed on 61 cm diameter cylinders without failure of the joint region.

MANUFACTURING DEVELOPMENT

The ARPA/ONR program aims to develop viable, affordable manufacturing processes capable of fabricating full-scale marine hull structures. Several automated, high quality, low cost, advanced fabrication methods were selected including thermoset and thermoplastic fiber placement, resin transfer molding of woven/braided stiffeners, and thermoforming/stamping and co-consolidation of thermoplastic stiffeners.

FIBER PLACEMENT PROCESSES

Fiber placement offers a low cost, automated fabrication technique lending itself to both thermoplastic and thermoset materials. The advantages of fiber placement includes the ability to make large complex structures like submersible hulls, to lay material at any fiber angle and any path and the ability to vary bandwidth. Precise, automated placement of fibers with multi-axes winders over complex mandrels and with in-situ consolidation will permit continuous, rapid, reproducible fabrication of submarine structures with relatively high throughputs and near zero porosity and precise resin control without use of on line vacuum bagging and autoclaving. In-situ consolidation will ultimately be coupled with real time in-process control will result in less rework and rejects of finished parts. Thermography and laser interferometric detection appear to be well suited techniques for real time identification of existing flaws and damage for filament wound/fiber placed configurations. The system can then identify anomalies before consecutive plies are wound over the flaw.

Auto consolidation of thermoplastics using fiber placement is being pursued by McDonnell Douglas Aerospace, Lockheed and General Dynamics/EBDiv. Thermoplastic fiber placement processing (figure 4), utilizes heat energy to simultaneously melt incoming feed material and the surface of the previously consolidated material. A pressure applicator then consolidates the thermoplastic in-situ and requires no further oven or autoclave processing. On-line NDI sensors track behind the applicator to provide real time in-process control.

SPHERICAL THERMOPLASTIC HULLS

Lockheed has responsibility for fabricating three subscale Access Spheres (1.22 meter diameter) and one full scale Access Sphere (2.13 meter diameter). These spheres contain two large openings at the poles that include titanium attachment rings that join the adjacent compartments [7]. Lockheed has been developing a multi-tow hybrid hot gas/hot shoe tape head for use with commercial graphite grade thermoplastic, AS4/PPS, prepreg tape. This process results in 870° C (1600° F) N2 gas pre/nip point heat with a hot shoe temperature of 538° C (1000° F). Lockheed also developed optimum winding patterns, stiffness and thickness spatial variations using the SPHERE winDER, SPIDER, Code. For the trial sphere, Lockheed is using a light weight frangible ceramic mandrel. Figure 5 depicts the fabrication of the 1.22 meter diameter sphere. Lockheed has completed a manufacturing trial sphere (Figure 6) including fiberglass padups and titanium attachment rings.

THERMOPLASTIC CYLINDERS

In addition to overall design agent responsibilities, GD/EBDiv. is fabricating a thermoplastic, stiffened, cylindrical hangar section of the CDDS. This is being performed with ICI Composite Structures and Automated Dynamics Corporation. Prior to fabricating the full scale CDDS articles, three subscale 1.22m (48 inch) diameter stiffened cylinders will be fabricated using the thermoplastic in-situ consolidation fiber placement technology. Both graphite PEEK, AS4/APC-2, and AS4/PPS material system were investigated. The equipment consists of a thermoplastic processing head (TPP) developed by ADC which uses nitrogen gas in a patented Hot Gas Torch to elevate the temperature of the matrix in the incoming tape or tow and the previous ply fiber being compacted by the compaction roller (Figure 7). Nitrogen gas is used to prevent oxidative degradation during the consolidation process. This process does not depend on incoming fiber tension. Consequently, material can be placed on open section geometries which have a single, double, or an infinite radius of curvature. Automated tape cut and splice capability of ADC's fiber placement heads results in several unique features which can be utilized during part fabrication which reduce cost and improve part quality. True axial reinforcement can be achieved on cylindrical geometries, without any special tooling requirements, such as pins located in the turn-

around regions. Helical plies can be placed with or without fiber crossovers. Accordingly, helical plies are not limited to biaxial plies. A positive or negative helical ply can be placed independent of one another. Ply drop-offs/build-ups can be placed within a structure. Also, within a ply, a tape path can be started or stopped to enhance wall thickness uniformity. This feature proves to be beneficial for closed geometries with non-constant cross-sections.

In working to achieve the high quality and high throughput goals of the ARPA program, ICI/ADC is performing on-going research and development activities to continuously improve the in-situ consolidation process. These activities consist of both process development and equipment development efforts. Process development efforts are aimed at maximizing the level of consolidation and determining the sensitivity of process parameters, while equipment development efforts are aimed at improving the economics (throughput) of the in-situ consolidation process. These efforts are presented in [8].

TEST ARTICLES

Prior to producing the 1.22m (48 inch) diameter test article, ICI fabricated a 61 cm (24 inch) diameter laboratory scale cylinder with three framing schemes a blade, "I" stiffener and "T" stiffened blade from APC-2/AS-4 thermoplastic material. The primary purpose of the laboratory scale cylinder was as a manufacturing demonstration and risk reduction article and to demonstrate various thermoplastic process technologies and stiffener concept fabrication while maintaining scale up considerations. These stiffening concepts were also representative of high throughput thermoplastic processing; i.e., thermoforming and stamping. The blade stiffener concept is composed of in-situ circumferential plies. The "I" stiffener includes quasi-isotropic webs and flanges to provide the necessary lateral load and attachment capabilities, which could not be provided by all hoop blade stiffeners. Inner and outer hoop flange caps are also included to provide the required continuous hoop strength. This fabrication technique permitted the percentages of quasi-isotropic and hoop plies to be optimized for the maximum performance and minimum weight.

The "I" frame stiffeners are formed from 90° segments of quasi-isotropic stamped channel sections which are placed back to back with a 45° segment overlap and co-consolidated in an integrally heated tool with an all hoop inner ring flange which is in-situ consolidated. The co-consolidated "I" frames are then placed in a segmented tool and overwrapped with an all hoop outer flange cap using in-situ consolidation. The stiffened cylinder is then completed by overwrapping all of the stiffeners in the segment mandrel with the hull lay-up. After all the hull plies have been placed, the core mandrel is extracted and the segmented mandrel is disassembled and removed. Based on strength and outfitting considerations, the "I" stiffener was selected for the 1.22 m diameter test article.

In addition to the 61 cm diameter fabrication demonstration laboratory model, GD/ICI/ADC produced two blade stiffened 61 cm diameter subscale collapse test models for CD/NSWC using AS4C/APC-2A material and one with AS4/PPS. One of these is shown in figure 8.

To mitigate risk and determine processing parameters for the 1.22 m (48 inch) diameter subscale cylinder, a manufacturing demonstration article with one "I" stiffener frame was fabricated. The tooling concept used in the manufacture of the 61 cm diameter subscale cylinder was scaled up to 1.22 m. The "I" stiffener was fabricated as discussed earlier. Figure 9 shows the completed frame assembly prior to being positioned on the core mandrel. The stiffener was held in alignment by the segmented tooling. The cylinder overwraps was in-situ consolidated directly over the stiffener assembly using AS4/APC-2, one inch (2.54 cm) slit tape for the required hull layup (Figure 10). The completed manufacturing demonstration article is shown in Figure 11. ADC is currently fabricating AS4/PPS "I"-stiffener assemblies using lessons learned from the fab demo article. These will then be assembled in a tool and the hull overwrap in-situ consolidated as discussed above. The model will be hydrostatically tested at CD/NSWC.

GD also designed and tested a 1.22 m diameter, 1.67 m long blade stiffened, non-autoclave cure, graphite/epoxy cylinder fabricated by Brunswick [9].

OTHER TEST ARTICLES

McDonnell Douglas is developing equipment and processes for the automated manufacturing of subscale test articles as well as full scale spheres and stiffened cylinders for the Composite Dry Deck Shelter. Three, subscale 1.22 m (48 inch) diameter subscale and one full scale, 2.13 m (84

inch) Hyperbaric spheres are being fabricated using the Cure-On-The-Fly™ (COTF™) fiber placement system for thermoset composites developed by Hercules. MTS is developing large scale resin transfer molding (RTM) for composite "I" stiffeners to integrally stiffen the forward hangar cylinder. MDA is building four subscale (1.22 m diameter) and one full-scale 2.74 m diameter Forward Hangar hulls, with the thermoplastic fiber placement process.

THERMOSET SPHERE

The COTF™ fiber placement being used by Hercules for the fabrication of the composite spheres is similar to the thermoplastic fiber placement process. Thermoset towpreg in a staged condition is guided to the fiber placement head where compaction pressure and heat energy is applied to cure the material as it is placed on the tool. After material placement, a subsequent oven post cure is utilized to achieve final material cross linking. COTF™ processing eliminates the labor intensive staged cure cycles previously required to make thick section composite parts. Hercules has fabricated two AS-4/3501-6 subscale spheres; a partial thickness process development sphere and one full thickness deliverable.

THERMOPLASTIC/THERMOSET CYLINDERS

The major components of the subscale stiffened cylinder are AS-4/APC-2 thermoplastic composite cylinder and eight resin transfer molded stiffening rings composite of an AS-4 woven/braided preform and Shell 1895 epoxy resin. The stiffener rings are made up of three 120° segments joined at a stiffener splice composed of composite and titanium. MDA will use thermoplastic fiber placement process and AS4/PPS material to fabricate the Forward Hangar subscale and full scale deliverables.

The three subcomponent deliverables will be fabricated on a five axis research and development machine (Figure 12). The machine is capable of placing 3.175 centimeter wide bands of material, has a fully automated band cut and add head for use with axial and off axis tow placement, and uses laser energy as the heat source. Figure 13 depicts the fabrication of the subscale thermoplastic cylinder.

The substructure of the subscale cylinder is stiffened by eight thermoset Resin Transfer Molding (RTM) "I" stiffening rings that are composed of three 120° segments. MTS is the subcontractor directing the fabrication of the stiffeners.

The RTM carbon fiber preform is made by a combination of weaving, braiding, and stitching. Weaving contributes the 0/90 fiber orientation, while braiding supplies the ±45 fiber orientation. Stitching is used to assemble and debulk the preform. Textile Technology, Inc. performs the weaving and Fiber Innovations supplies the braiding and stitching. The curved preforms are near net shape when loaded into the RTM preform.

The RTM processing of the stiffeners is being performed by Brunswick. In the RTM process the "I" stiffener is oriented in the tool on its side. After demolding the part is near net shape. Presses and autoclaves are not required, making this process very scaleable to a larger size parts.

The "I" stiffener segments are adhesively bonded to the thermoplastic cylinder. Since the stiffeners are thermoset, MDA conducted an extensive investigation into the adhesive selection and bonding process [11]. The process selected allows all eight stiffeners and associated flange straps to be bonded simultaneously. Figure 14 shows the completed thermoplastic cylinder with the bonded thermoset stiffeners. To verify the design, manufacturing and analysis techniques, the 1.22 m stiffened cylinder was strain gaged and subjected to external hydrostatic pressure tests at CDNSWC (Figure 15). The cylinder successfully attained a collapse pressure 20% greater than the design collapse pressure with a predictable failure mode. Figure 16 shows the cylinder for post test inspection with circumferential damage at the center of the cylinder and along a longitude. To obtain in-service experience for marine composites, to leverage the ARPA technology and reduce costs, this 1.22 m stiffened cylinder design was selected for the ONR Composite Storage Capsule.

THERMOSET HANGAR DOOR

Northrup Grumman is developing the fabrication of the subscale hangar door articles and full scale deliverable. The material system is IM7/E7T1-2 toughened graphite epoxy with inner and outer layers of fiberglass for galvanic coupling and damage detection. The monocoque, variable thickness ellipsoidal shell incorporates an annealed 6Al-4V titanium stepped bonded ring using FM300 -1K adhesive. A subscale 1.22 m diameter door was fabricated by R-Cubed using tape

winding, tape and tow prep placement and fabric. The door varies in thickness from 35.8 mm (1.41 in) at the equator to 65.5 mm (2.58 in) at the crown. Figure 17 shows the elliptical subscale door in the test stand prior to being lowered into the test tank at CD/NSWC. The door successfully sustained an external pressure load 5% greater than the design collapse pressure and failed as predicted, figure 18.

To capitalize on this successful test and reduce development and fabrication costs, this 1.22 m diameter door design was chosen as the closure door, for the ONR Composite Storage Capsule.

SUMMARY

Composite materials for marine structures offer the potential benefits of reduced weight and maintenance, improved stealth and survivability over existing metal structures. The low cost, high quality, scaleable, automated processing being utilized by ARPA to manufacture the proof-of-concept articles has demonstrated the feasibility of fabricating marine structures of advanced composites. Numerous processes and many lessons learned have been obtained through the building block approach. Leveraging on the successful design and fabrication technology demonstrated on the subscale models, Office of Naval Research has undertaken to develop a Composite Storage Capsule as a useful near term application.

The ONR Composite Storage Capsule will provide cyclic, underwater explosion and in-service experience to establish a high level of confidence in the design, inspection and manufacturing processes and will serve as a stepping stone for future composite technology advancements and for full scale Composite Dry Deck Shelter fabrication.

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Figure 1 - ARPA CDDS Participants

Figure 2 - ARPA Composite Dry Deck Shelter

Figure 3 - ONR Composite Storage Capsule

Figure 4 - In-Situ Consolidation Fiber Placement Process

Figure 5 - Thermoplastic Fiber Placement Variable Axis Support Arm

Figure 6 - 1.22 m Trial Sphere with Titanium Attachment Rings

Figure 7 - ADC Hot Gas Torch Head

Figure 8 - 61 cm Diameter AS4c/APC-2A Lab Model

Figure 9 - Stamped, Co-Consolidated, 1.22 m Dia. and 61 cm Dia. AS4/APC-2 Stiffeners

Figure 10 - Thermoplastic Overwrap of 1.22 m Diameter Stiffener and Shell

Figure 11 - 1.22m Diameter Manufacturing Demo

Figure 12 - MDA-E Thermoplastic Placement Machine

Figure 13 - Thermoplastic Cylinder Fabrication

Figure 14 - Thermoplastic Cylinder with RTM Bonded Stiffeners Model

Figure 15 - Thermoplastic Model Being Lowered into Test Tank at CDNSWC

Figure 16 - Thermoplastic Stiffened Cylinder Following Successful Collapse Test

Figure 17 - Elliptical Hangar Door 1.22 Model Prior to Test

Figure 18 - Elliptical Hangar Door Showing Damage After Successful Test